

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL CONTENT OF PUBLIC CONTROL

Manzurakhan Yunusova

PhD candidate in social philosophy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7559954>

Abstract: The socio-philosophical content of public control is very broad and includes issues such as social initiative, motivation and responsibility. Through the implementation of public control, the potential of the neighborhood in socio-economic development increases.

Key words: Community control, neighborhood, social initiative, responsibility, promotion.

The object of public control is one of the more stable socio-political institutions. In simple terms, the subject's ability to exert influence on the object covering the activities of state bodies can be described as follows.

First, the official positions of the self-governing body are usually occupied by people from other professions, after many years of work. Probably because of this, not everyone is fully aware of the legislation in this field. In this regard, the main support remains the national political culture. That is, only the knowledge of the head of the neighborhood before the election can be the basis for effective public control. In order to solve the problems in this regard, the Ministry of Neighborhood and Nurani Support has organized one-week training courses, in which the activists of the neighborhood will be fully trained on the actual problems encountered in their activities. The training modules also include lessons on the organization of public control.

Secondly, the political and legal status of the self-governing bodies - the neighborhood, while the social status in the society is clear - remains very complicated. Leaving detailed legal analyzes in this regard to the discretion of jurists, we will dwell on the complications in the implementation of public control. In particular, it is observed that the subject of neighborhood public control, nominally as an organization in the system of the neighborhood support department in the local authority, faces difficulties in controlling the authority. Usually, the chairman of the neighborhood has to work closely with the local authorities to solve the problems in the neighborhood. Because it is not the official status and powers to solve the current issues, but also the informal relations and the reputation of the neighborhood chairpersons in their previous work activities. It is probably for this reason that the activists of community assemblies do not always refer to the legal mechanisms of public control. Solving problems depends on the authority of the chairmen and the attitude of the officials to the work process. Because the important issue in this process is " ...determining and maintaining mutual boundaries between civil society and the state: expanding social equality and freedom and democratizing state institutions and forming new structures " [1].

Third, although public control mechanisms are established by law, liability for non-compliance is not established. This leads to the fact that local authorities do not always pay attention to public initiatives. For example, let's focus on public hearings, which are most common in self-governing bodies of public control. "A public hearing is a meeting organized to discuss issues related to the activities of state bodies, their officials, and of social importance,

or to the rights and legal interests of citizens, legal entities, and the interests of society"[2]. Currently, under the motto "People should serve the people, not the state agencies, the state agencies should serve the people" by holding receptions of citizens in the neighborhoods of the state authorities and taking measures to solve certain problems. In addition, on the initiative of the head of state, all households were registered on the basis of "neighborhood". Special structures in higher state agencies are involved in solving problems. A number of factors hinder the full functioning of the institution of public hearing, which allows solving problems in the neighborhood on a systematic basis without the participation of higher organizations. In particular, responsibility for non-implementation of the decision taken at the end of the public hearing was not established. In addition, it is evident that the neighborhood lacks a certain experience in sorting out the problems of the citizens and separating the most necessary ones. Because of this, it is very difficult to focus on the most important issues in important meetings related to the life of the community. As most scholars have pointed out, one of the important interpretations of civil society is self-organization, the ability to harmonize the interests of different social groups and unite them in decision-making [3].

It should be noted that the existing problems create prospects for the implementation of public control in Uzbekistan and are among the factors that serve to increase the initiative of its subjects.

In Uzbekistan, there are a number of ways to implement public control by community assemblies.

Public discussion will consist of "public discussion of issues of social importance, as well as drafts of normative legal documents, other decisions of state bodies"[3]. It is known that most of the issues that are put to public discussion are programs financed by the state authorities. At this point, issues of comprehensive support for quality and successful implementation of these programs are very relevant. In different regions of the world, in the process of public control, there are models of conducting opposition or support policies in relation to the authorities. In European countries, public activists are opposed to the authorities, while in the USA they show their support for the political authorities [4]. In Uzbekistan, the neighborhood is seriously considering the work of comprehensive support of state programs and the construction of certain facilities at its own expense from the national budget. This was especially evident within the "Initiative budget" project in the open budget system. This project was able to show that Uzbekistan has huge resources for supporting civil initiatives and their implementation, and if the work is properly organized and successful experiences are used, public representatives will be very active. According to the Ministry of Finance, about 20 million citizens participated in the voting, about 70,000 initiatives were received, and more than 1 trillion 201 billion soums were allocated for financing[5]. In some cases, experts of different levels give different conclusions on the level of formation of political culture and democratic values. Such projects have shown that the people of our country can adopt even the most advanced democratic initiatives in a short period of time. Through this nationwide public discussion, it became clear that it is possible to involve a wide range of people in solving the problems in the neighborhoods.

A public hearing is a meeting organized to discuss issues related to the activities of state bodies, their officials and of social importance, or to the rights and legal interests of citizens, legal entities, and the interests of society.[6] Public hearing is a very convenient instrument for conveying the existing problems of the neighborhood to the citizens of the area, gathering

and mobilizing their strength and capabilities, and solving them together with the authorities. This practice allows citizens to gather in a certain place, bring their problems to the authorities, and negotiate among themselves. As a result of the public hearing, it is necessary for people to express their opinion under equal conditions, to establish a communication dialogue between civil servants and citizens, to make rational decisions and to form a reflexive public opinion [7]. It is known that although the public is fully aware of the existing problems, it may not have a complete idea of its origin and solution. Especially in the current global information environment, there are cases of different interpretations of the situation by different sources and the distribution of populist messages. Only equal communication between the authorities and people's representatives can create certain ideas about the origin and solution of the problem. At the end of this dialogue, regardless of the solution of the problem, there may be a positive change in public opinion.

According to Y. Habermas, an expert on public hearing:

1. To open and continue the topic of discussion on the problems of public concern of all citizens;
2. Participant - citizens should be organized on the basis of equal rights in expressing their opinions and putting forward their proposals, arguing and criticizing the proposals of others.[8]

As a school of democracy, the neighborhood should show all its aspects precisely within the framework of public hearings. At the same time, the lack of legislation and methodology for organizing public hearings in Uzbekistan is also a problem. Based on the characteristics of the neighborhood and the essence of the established values, the development of model regulations on public hearing in the neighborhoods and its delivery to the activists of the neighborhood is one of the current issues. In this regard, the project "Development of rural infrastructure" implemented within the framework of the agreement signed between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the World Bank can be an example. Elements of the methodology developed by Bridget Bode, an expert on the mobilization of US public initiatives, can be used. Within the framework of this successful project, "The project will be implemented in 5 regions, and the appropriation of funds will be 1.3 million in 306 neighborhood assemblies. coverage of the population is planned, direct participation of the population is ensured in the process of selecting sub-projects in these areas" [9]. The application of international experience is becoming a necessity in the process of the new image of the neighborhood, its transformation into a center of services and services.

One of the important issues at the community meetings is the issue of listening to the report of the prevention inspector of the internal affairs bodies and the information of the heads of the family polyclinic in the area. In addition, within the framework of public control, neighborhoods hear reports of all organizations in the area on environmental protection, sanitary condition of the area, beautification and greening. According to the results of the conducted monitoring, the reports of the leaders of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent on issues related to the activity of neighborhoods were heard 7652 times at the citizens' meetings, and a number of issues related to the regions were positively resolved. 6,380 reports of heads of enterprises, institutions and organizations in the regions were heard on the issues of beautification. At the same time, 182 sessions of regional, district (city) Councils of People's Deputies discussed issues related to improving the efficiency of citizens' self-government bodies, and appropriate decisions were made[10].

The effectiveness of public control, the most important factor that forms public opinion about it, is the issue of monitoring the implementation of the adopted decisions. It is known that decisions are made based on the results of public discussions and hearings, sending requests to state authorities according to the current procedures. However, the issues of monitoring the implementation of the decisions made using information technologies and taking legal measures against officials who have not implemented them are still open. For this reason, the Code of Administrative Responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan should establish liability for non-implementation of decisions made at the meeting of neighborhood citizens on the basis of public control. At the same time, it will be necessary to integrate the decisions made in this way at community meetings into a single platform, to attach the control of this platform to the agencies responsible for communication with the people.

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